

CYTOGENETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ALLOPOLYPLOID FORMS F₂C (*G.HERBACEUM* SUBSP. *FRUTESCENS* × *G.MUSTELINUM*)

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ANNOTATION: Representatives of the diploid *G. herbaceum* L. species of cotton are resistant to pests and insects, and the fibers of the tetraploid *G. mustelinum* species are naturally colored, ripe and thin. Therefore, they are a valuable source for enriching the genotype of cultivated cotton varieties grown in our country. This article presents the results of cytogenetic analysis of allopolyploid forms F₂C (*Gossypium herbaceum* subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum*). The obtained hybrid combinations determine the potential of genomic variability and provide an opportunity to select parental forms for breeding.

KEYWORDS: cotton, species, cytogenetics, chromosome, meiosis, sporad, meiotic index, micronuclear tetrad, polyad.

The cytogenetic studies conducted on Gossypium L. have been an important scientific direction in cotton cultivation for many years. Cytogenetic analyses, including chromosome conjugation during the metaphase I stage of meiosis, analysis of spores, and investigation of pollen viability, are among the most effective methods for determining the ploidy of intergeneric hybrids.

Numerous studies have been conducted on the chromosome set of cotton and the processes during their division. The chromosome morphology of *Gossypium hirsutum* L. and *Gossypium barbadense* L. has been analyzed, demonstrating that the study of chromosome conjugation is essential for ensuring the genetic stability of cotton [1].

Cytogenetic analyses conducted on intergeneric F₁ and F₂ hybrids involving diploid and tetraploid cotton species have shown that abnormalities occur during the metaphase I stage. In some hybrids, disruptions such as univalents of varying sizes, ring-shaped quadrivalents, low meiotic indices, and the occurrence of abnormal tetrads alongside micro-nucleated tetrads have been observed during the conjugation process [2].

One of the distinctive characteristics of hybrids formed from the crossing of distantly related shapes is the disruption of chromosome conjugation during the meiosis process. In such cases, the disruption of conjugation is related to the absence of homologous chromosomes from different species or the presence of only partially homologous ones. Hybrids with homeologous genomes are viable but are sterile due to the polyploid nature of their genomes, meaning they are unable to produce offspring [4].

One of the key traits that determine the productivity of generations is pollen viability. Assessing the viability of pollen and establishing its optimal conditions is a critical factor in obtaining plant seeds. The successful formation of seeds depends not only on the abundance of pollen but also on its viability. Evaluating the quality of pollen during the flowering phase allows for an assessment of their reproductive potential [3].

It is well known that pollen grains produced as a result of improper meiosis are not equal in terms of hereditary traits and functional capabilities. When the chromosome complex is insufficient, meaning the frequency of homologous chromosome pairing is low, viable pollen grains develop poorly, and sterility significantly increases. However, when a complete chromosome complex is restored, meaning the homologous chromosome series is intact, pollen grains regain their viability [7].

In the studies of selection, cytobiology, and experimental polyploidy, the structure of flowers and pollen viability are considered important. The pollen grains produced and maturing in the anthers play a crucial role in the sexual reproduction of plants. Studying this provides genetic information about the plant's ability to form in nature and its potential to produce future generations [6].

Research materials and methods

Experimental research work was carried out in the Laboratory of Experimental Polyploidy and Phylogeny of Cotton of the Institute of Genetics and Experimental Biology of Plants of the Republic of

Uzbekistan.

The analysis of maternal pollen mother cells (PMC) during the metaphase I (MI) stage of meiosis, as well as pollen viability and spore analyses, was conducted using the method described by Pausheva Z.P. [5]. In this process, flower buds measuring 2-4 mm were collected between 9-10 AM, and fixed in a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid at a 3:7 ratio. Temporary preparations were made using acetocarmine stain with a light microscope. The materials were sorted into the necessary stages through initial selection. In the analysis of tetrads, the meiotic index, which is the proportion of normal tetrads to the total number of spores, was calculated.

To determine pollen viability, flowers that opened in the first half of the day, specifically between 10-11 AM, were collected. Preparations were made from fresh pollen grains each time. Acetocarmine stain was used for coloring the pollen grains. To enhance the staining of viable pollen grains, they were placed in Petri dishes and stored in a refrigerator for one day. Each preparation was analyzed in 10 viewing fields. Cytological analyses were conducted using a Leica CM E microscope equipped with a Leica EC3 camera.

The results obtained

During the research, cytogenetic analyses were conducted on F₂C allopolyploid hybrids formed by crossing the diploid *Gossypium herbaceum* and the tetraploid *Gossypium mustelinum*.

In the allopolyploid forms of *F₂C subsp. frutescens × G. mustelinum*, various samples were identified regarding the ploidy of maternal pollen mother cells during the MI stage of meiosis, showing chromosome conjugation (24.75±0.29; 38.18±0.23; 38.19±0.27). Such disruptions contribute to partial sterility of the allopolyploid hybrids and the emergence of abnormal spores during the sporad stage (see Table 1).

Table 1

Conjugation of chromosomes in metaphase-I stage of meiosis

№	polypl oid forms	Th e number of studied maternal pollen cells, pcs	For each cell		
			number of univalents, pcs	number of bivalents, pcs	number of quadriva- tapes, pcs
F₂C allopolyploid hybrid forms					
5	T 37-14 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G.mustelinum</i>	30	5 1,46±0,5	9 24,75±0,2	9 0,26±0,0
6	T 38-3 <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G.mustelinum</i>	23	-	0 26,00±0,0	-
7	T 37-4 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G.mustelinum</i>	28	5 0,64±0,2	3 38,18±0,2	1 0,25±0,1
8	T 49-2 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G.mustelinum</i>	22	7 0,54±0,2	7 38,19±0,2	3 0,27±0,1
9	T 30-8 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G.mustelinum</i>	18	-	0 26,00±0,0	-

In the allopolyploid hybrid plants of F₂C subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum*, both normal and abnormal samples were identified during the MI stage of meiosis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Chromosome conjugation during the metaphase I stage of meiosis: F₂C *G. herbaceum* subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum*. a) – 23^{II} + 6^I; b) – 26^{II}

In certain F₂C allopolyploid hybrids, the analysis of tetrads revealed that the meiotic index was higher compared to F₁C hexaploid hybrids. In the allopolyploids T 30-7 subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum* and T 38-3 subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum*, the meiotic index was found to be 98.51-98.54%, with no occurrences of micro-nucleated tetrads, and the amount of polyads ranged from 1.42% to 1.48% (Table 2).

Table 2

Analysis of tetrads in F₁C and F₂C allopolyploid hybrid forms.

	Hybrid combinations	total number of spores, pcs	meiotic index, %	micro nuclear tetrads, %	poly des, %
F₁C hexaploid hybrids					
	subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	12	6 90,3 6±1,19	3,2 7±0,72	6,37 ±0,98
F₂C allopolyploid hybrids					
	T 1-8 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	11	4 96,1 5±0,12	0,8 9±0,41	3,07 ±0,72
	T 38-12 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	25	3 97,0 5±0,64	-	2,62 ±0,29
0	T 30-6 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	54	3 97,2 1±0,47	-	2,78 ±0,71
1	T 51-13 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	98	2 97,4 5±0,88	0,6 9±0,23	2,11 ±0,41
2	T 30-7 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	41	3 98,5 1±0,48	-	1,48 ±0,44
3	T 30-8 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	05	4 96,0 5±0,88	-	3,12 ±0,79
4	T 38-3 subsp. <i>frutescens</i> × <i>G. mustelinum</i>	57	3 98,5 4±0,81	-	1,42 ±0,38

In the allopolyploid hybrid F₂C subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum*, pollen viability was studied in 24 out of 134 plants. Most of the hybrid plants exhibited a demand for short-day conditions and late flowering. By late autumn, many hybrids did not develop generative organs, and abnormal forms were observed. In some hybrids that began to flower, pollen development was impaired, and underdeveloped pollen grains were noted (Table 3).

In the studied hybrids, the level of pollen viability varied significantly, with 14 hybrids showing low viability (1.49-40.43%). Among these, the plants T 33-6, T 30-8, T 49-2, and T 38-7 exhibited particularly low viability (1.49-10.23%). Meanwhile, plants T 33-2 and T 37-4 reached pollen viability levels of up to 50% or more, while T 38-3, T 30-6, T 30-7, and T 38-12 showed pollen viability rates exceeding 60% (see Table 3).

Table 3.

F₂C subsp. frutescens × G. mustelinum in allopolyploid hybrids dust viability analysis.

	№	total number of pollens, pcs	Pollen viability, %		№	total number of pollens, pcs	Pollen viability, %
1-13	T	119	33,86 ± 1,87	30-8	T	2955	55,74 ± 0,83
1-4	T	700	40,43 ± 3,44	37-4	T	482	50,21 ± 5,18
1-8	T	482	51,04 ± 5,18	37-8	T	796	23,12 ± 2,23
30-23	T	538	27,14 ± 3,67	38-12	T	846	60,87 ± 2,81
30-6	T	666	60,21 ± 3,59	38-3	T	1315	67,76 ± 1,66
30-7	T	738	65,85 ± 3,04	38-4	T	367	38,42 ± 6,44
37-14	T	114	7,89 ± 6,37	38-7	T	352	10,23 ± 2,60
30-1	T	267	22,85 ± 6,60	42-2	T	159	14,47 ± 7,78
33-2	T	690	46,8 ± 3,60	49-2	T	606	1,49 ± 0,24
33-6	T	248	5,65 ± 21,14	51-15	T	426	34,27 ± 5,28
36-1	T	76	15,79 ± 17,49	51-19	T	363	25,07 ± 5,17
37-2	T	228	17,54 ± 6,34	51-13	T	1536	51,76 ± 1,62

In the studied F₂C subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum* polyploid hybrids, pollen viability varied significantly, with the following levels identified: T 1-4 at 40.4%, T 37-4 at 50.2%, T 49-2 at 1.5%, and T 37-14 at 7.9% (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Analysis of pollen viability in plants of F₂C subsp. *frutescens* × *G. mustelinum*: a) T 1-4 – 40,4%; b) T 37-4- 50,2%; c) T 49-2 -1,5%; d) T 37-14- 7,9%.

Conclusions

Thus, based on the results of cytogenetic analyses of the F2C hybrids formed from the crossing of distantly related species, we can conclude the following: The analysis of tetrads revealed high meiotic indices in nearly all plants. However, these hybrids also exhibited various meiotic anomalies (such as micro-nucleated tetrads and polyads), along with low levels of pollen viability.

As a result of studying pollen viability, relatively high levels of this trait ($67.76 \pm 1.66\%$) were observed among the F2C subsp. **frutescens** × **G. mustelinum** allopolyploid hybrids. The presence of such plants indicates the formation of a balanced chromosome set, alongside minor structural anomalies in the hybrids.

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